

Supplementary File 1

Documentation of the Article Screening Process: PubMed Database

This document is provided to ensure full transparency and reproducibility of the article selection process, as detailed in the PRISMA diagram (Figure 1) and the Methods section of the main manuscript. It contains the complete list of all articles initially identified in the PubMed database search.

Legend for Screening Decisions

Each article in the list below is color-coded to indicate the outcome of the screening process. The totals correspond to the numbers presented in the study selection diagram.

- **Blue highlight:** Article was selected for full-text reading and was **included** in the final review. **(Total: 43)**
- **Red highlight:** Article was **excluded** during the title and abstract screening phase as it did not meet the pre-defined inclusion criteria. **(Total: 26)**
- **Orange highlight:** Article was identified as a **duplicate** of a record from another database and was removed prior to the screening phase. **(Total: 11)**

1: Haake DA, Levett PN. Leptospirosis in humans. *Curr Top Microbiol Immunol*. 2015;387:65-97. doi: 10.1007/978-3-662-45059-8_5. PMID: 25388133; PMCID: PMC4442676.

2: Selvarajah S, Ran S, Roberts NW, Nair M. Leptospirosis in pregnancy: A systematic review. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2021 Sep 14;15(9):e0009747. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0009747. PMID: 34520461; PMCID: PMC8462732.

3: Antima, Banerjee S. Modeling the dynamics of leptospirosis in India. *Sci Rep*. 2023 Nov 13;13(1):19791. doi: 10.1038/s41598-023-46326-2. PMID: 37957218; PMCID: PMC10643689.

4: Mwachui MA, Crump L, Hartskeerl R, Zinsstag J, Hattendorf J. Environmental and Behavioural Determinants of Leptospirosis Transmission: A Systematic Review. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2015 Sep 17;9(9):e0003843. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0003843. PMID: 26379035; PMCID: PMC4574979.

5: Cunha M, Costa F, Ribeiro GS, Carvalho MS, Reis RB, Nery N Jr, Pischel L, Gouveia EL, Santos AC, Queiroz A, Wunder EA Jr, Reis MG, Diggle PJ, Ko AI. Rainfall and other meteorological factors as drivers of urban transmission of leptospirosis. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2022 Apr 11;16(4):e0007507. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0007507. PMID: 35404948; PMCID: PMC9022820.

6: Lotto Batista M, Rees EM, Gómez A, López S, Castell S, Kucharski AJ, Ghazzi S, Müller GV, Lowe R. Towards a leptospirosis early warning system in northeastern Argentina. *J R Soc Interface*. 2023 May;20(202):20230069. doi: 10.1098/rsif.2023.0069. Epub 2023 May 17. PMID: 37194269; PMCID: PMC10189304.

7: Miller E, Barragan V, Chiriboga J, Weddell C, Luna L, Jiménez DJ, Aleman J,

Mihaljevic JR, Olivas S, Marks J, Izurieta R, Nieto N, Keim P, Trueba G, Caporaso JG, Pearson T. *Leptospira* in river and soil in a highly endemic area of Ecuador. *BMC Microbiol.* 2021 Jan 7;21(1):17. doi: 10.1186/s12866-020-02069-y. PMID: 33413126; PMCID: PMC7792295.

8: Nardoni Marteli A, Guasselli LA, Diamant D, Wink GO, Vasconcelos VV. Spatio-temporal analysis of leptospirosis in Brazil and its relationship with flooding. *Geospat Health.* 2022 Nov 29;17(2). doi: 10.4081/gh.2022.1128. PMID: 36468592.

9: Mejía L, Prado B, Cárdenas P, Trueba G, González-Candelas F. The impact of genetic recombination on pathogenic *Leptospira*. *Infect Genet Evol.* 2022 Aug;102:105313. doi: 10.1016/j.meegid.2022.105313. Epub 2022 Jun 7. PMID: 35688386.

10: Barragan V, Olivas S, Keim P, Pearson T. Critical Knowledge Gaps in Our Understanding of Environmental Cycling and Transmission of *Leptospira* spp. *Appl Environ Microbiol.* 2017 Sep 15;83(19):e01190-17. doi: 10.1128/AEM.01190-17. PMID: 28754706; PMCID: PMC5601346.

11: Chou LF, Chen TW, Yang HY, Tian YC, Chang MY, Hung CC, Lai CH, Hsu SH, Tsai CY, Ko YC, Lian JH, Yang CW. Implication of the IL-10-Expression Signature in the Pathogenicity of *Leptospira*-Infected Macrophages. *Microbiol Spectr.* 2022 Jun 29;10(3):e0259521. doi: 10.1128/spectrum.02595-21. Epub 2022 May 31. PMID: 35638785; PMCID: PMC9241676.

12: Baquero OS, Machado G. Spatiotemporal dynamics and risk factors for human Leptospirosis in Brazil. *Sci Rep.* 2018 Oct 11;8(1):15170. doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-33381-3. Erratum in: *Sci Rep.* 2019 May 1;9(1):7000. doi: 10.1038/s41598-019-42747-0. PMID: 30310115; PMCID: PMC6181921.

13: Cano-Pérez E, Loyola S, Espitia-Almeida F, Torres-Pacheco J, Malambo-García D, Gómez-Camargo D. Climatic Variability and Human Leptospirosis Cases in Cartagena, Colombia: A 10-Year Ecological Study. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2021 Dec 6;106(3):785-791. doi: 10.4269/ajtmh.21-0890. PMID: 34872058; PMCID: PMC8922519.

14: Chadsuthi S, Chalvet-Monfray K, Wiratsudakul A, Modchang C. The effects of flooding and weather conditions on leptospirosis transmission in Thailand. *Sci Rep.* 2021 Jan 15;11(1):1486. doi: 10.1038/s41598-020-79546-x. PMID: 33452273; PMCID: PMC7810882.

15: Motto SK, Hernandez-Castro LE, Shirima GM, Mengele IJ, Bwatota SF, Bronsvort BMC, Lyatuu ET, Komwihangilo DM, Cook EAJ. Seroepidemiology of *Leptospira* serovar Hardjo and associated risk factors in smallholder dairy cattle in Tanzania. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* 2023 Apr 5;17(4):e0011199. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0011199. PMID: 37018175; PMCID: PMC10075398.

16: Suwanpakdee S, Kaewkungwal J, White LJ, Asensio N, Ratanakorn P,

Singhasivanon P, Day NP, Pan-Ngum W. Spatio-temporal patterns of leptospirosis in Thailand: is flooding a risk factor? *Epidemiol Infect.* 2015 Jul;143(10):2106-15. doi: 10.1017/S0950268815000205. Epub 2015 Mar 17. PMID: 25778527; PMCID: PMC4462160.

17: Baharom M, Ahmad N, Hod R, Arsad FS, Tangang F. The Impact of Meteorological Factors on Communicable Disease Incidence and Its Projection: A Systematic Review. *Int J Environ Res Public Health.* 2021 Oct 22;18(21):11117. doi: 10.3390/ijerph182111117. PMID: 34769638; PMCID: PMC8583681.

18: Douchet L, Menkes C, Herbreteau V, Larrieu J, Bador M, Goarant C, Mangeas M. Climate-driven models of leptospirosis dynamics in tropical islands from three oceanic basins. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* 2024 Apr 25;18(4):e0011717. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0011717. PMID: 38662800; PMCID: PMC11075899.

19: Ma Y, Destouni G, Kalantari Z, Omazic A, Evengård B, Berggren C, Thierfelder T. Linking climate and infectious disease trends in the Northern/Arctic Region. *Sci Rep.* 2021 Oct 19;11(1):20678. doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-00167-z. PMID: 34667214; PMCID: PMC8526576.

20: Warnasekara J, Agampodi S, Abeynayake R. Time series models for prediction of leptospirosis in different climate zones in Sri Lanka. *PLoS One.* 2021 May 14;16(5):e0248032. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0248032. Erratum in: *PLoS One.* 2025 Jan 23;20(1):e0318175. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0318175. PMID: 33989292; PMCID: PMC8121312.

21: Yanagihara Y, Villanueva SYAM, Nomura N, Ohno M, Sekiya T, Handabile C, Shingai M, Higashi H, Yoshida SI, Masuzawa T, Gloriani NG, Saito M, Kida H. *Leptospira* Is an Environmental Bacterium That Grows in Waterlogged Soil. *Microbiol Spectr.* 2022 Apr 27;10(2):e0215721. doi: 10.1128/spectrum.02157-21. Epub 2022 Mar 15. PMID: 35289672; PMCID: PMC9045322.

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23: Benacer D, Thong KL, Min NC, Bin Verasahib K, Galloway RL, Hartskeerl RA, Souris M, Mohd Zain SN. Epidemiology of human leptospirosis in Malaysia, 2004-2012. *Acta Trop.* 2016 May;157:162-8. doi: 10.1016/j.actatropica.2016.01.031. Epub 2016 Feb 1. PMID: 26844370.

24: Sánchez-Montes S, Espinosa-Martínez DV, Ríos-Muñoz CA, Berzunza-Cruz M, Becker I. Leptospirosis in Mexico: Epidemiology and Potential Distribution of Human Cases. *PLoS One.* 2015 Jul 24;10(7):e0133720. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0133720. PMID: 26207827; PMCID: PMC4514770.

- 25: Major A, Schweighauser A, Francey T. Increasing incidence of canine leptospirosis in Switzerland. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2014 Jul 16;11(7):7242-60. doi: 10.3390/ijerph110707242. PMID: 25032740; PMCID: PMC4113873.
- 26: Cremonese C, Souza FN, Palma FAG, Sodré JFA, Brito RL, Ribeiro PDS, Santana JO, Coelho RH, Ticona JPA, Nazaré RJ, de Oliveira D, Silva CQ, Eyre MT, Mendes VA, Knee J, Ristow P, Stauber CE, López YAA, Giorgi E, Diggle PJ, Reis MGG, Cumming O, Ko A, Costa F. Simplified sewerage to prevent urban leptospirosis transmission: a cluster non-randomised controlled trial protocol in disadvantaged urban communities of Salvador, Brazil. *BMJ Open*. 2023 Jun 23;13(6):e065009. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2022-065009. PMID: 37355266; PMCID: PMC10314607.
- 27: Martins M, Lacerda MV, Monteiro WM, Moura MA, Santos EC, Saraceni V, Saraiva MG. Progression of the load of waterborne and intestinal parasitic diseases in the State of Amazonas. *Rev Soc Bras Med Trop*. 2015;48 Suppl 1:42-54. doi: 10.1590/0037-8682-0162-2014. PMID: 26061370.
- 28: Mohd Radi MF, Hashim JH, Jaafar MH, Hod R, Ahmad N, Mohammed Nawi A, Baloch GM, Ismail R, Farakhin Ayub NI. Leptospirosis Outbreak After the 2014 Major Flooding Event in Kelantan, Malaysia: A Spatial-Temporal Analysis. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2018 May;98(5):1281-1295. doi: 10.4269/ajtmh.16-0922. Epub 2018 Mar 8. PMID: 29532771; PMCID: PMC5953347.
- 29: Casanovas-Massana A, Costa F, Riediger IN, Cunha M, de Oliveira D, Mota DC, Sousa E, Querino VA, Nery N Jr, Reis MG, Wunder EA Jr, Diggle PJ, Ko AI. Spatial and temporal dynamics of pathogenic *Leptospira* in surface waters from the urban slum environment. *Water Res*. 2018 Mar 1;130:176-184. doi: 10.1016/j.watres.2017.11.068. Epub 2017 Nov 30. PMID: 29220718; PMCID: PMC5767135.
- 30: Rees EM, Lau CL, Kama M, Reid S, Lowe R, Kucharski AJ. Estimating the duration of antibody positivity and likely time of *Leptospira* infection using data from a cross-sectional serological study in Fiji. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2022 Jun 13;16(6):e0010506. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0010506. PMID: 35696427; PMCID: PMC9232128.
- 31: Hagiya H, Koyama T, Otsuka F. Epidemiological Characteristics and Trends in the Incidence of Leptospirosis in Japan: A Nationwide, Observational Study from 2006 to 2021. *Am J Trop Med Hyg*. 2023 Jul 24;109(3):589-594. doi: 10.4269/ajtmh.23-0131. PMID: 37487568; PMCID: PMC10484259.
- 32: Weinberger D, Baroux N, Grangeon JP, Ko AI, Goarant C. El Niño Southern Oscillation and leptospirosis outbreaks in New Caledonia. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2014 Apr 17;8(4):e2798. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0002798. PMID: 24743322;

PMCID: PMC3990495.

33: García-Méndez J, Cervera-Ceballos E, Atilano-López D, Arroyo-Escalante S, Moncada-Barrón D, Leyva-Leyva M, Hernández-Castro R, Carrillo-Casas EM. Leptospirosis in an asplenic patient -case report. *BMC Infect Dis.* 2020 Feb 28;20(1):186. doi: 10.1186/s12879-020-4869-3. PMID: 32111168; PMCID: PMC7048021.

34: Wunder EA, Adhikarla H, Hamond C, Owers Bonner KA, Liang L, Rodrigues CB, Bisht V, Nally JE, Alt DP, Reis MG, Diggle PJ, Felgner PL, Ko A. A live attenuated-vaccine model confers cross-protective immunity against different species of the *Leptospira* genus. *Elife.* 2021 Jan 26;10:e64166. doi: 10.7554/eLife.64166. PMID: 33496263; PMCID: PMC7837694.

35: Arias-Monsalve C, Builes-Jaramillo A. Impact of El Niño-Southern oscillation on human leptospirosis in Colombia at different spatial scales. *J Infect Dev Ctries.* 2019 Dec 31;13(12):1108-1116. doi: 10.3855/jidc.11702. PMID: 32088698.

36: Garcia M, Gopalakrishna KV. A Case of Imported Leptospirosis: Rhabdomyolysis and Severe Hyperbilirubinemia in a Traveler Returning From Puerto Rico. *Cureus.* 2023 Feb 6;15(2):e34690. doi: 10.7759/cureus.34690. PMID: 36909049; PMCID: PMC9994765.

37: Togami E, Kama M, Goarant C, Craig SB, Lau C, Ritter JM, Imrie A, Ko AI, Nilles EJ. A Large Leptospirosis Outbreak following Successive Severe Floods in Fiji, 2012. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2018 Oct;99(4):849-851. doi: 10.4269/ajtmh.18-0335. PMID: 30141390; PMCID: PMC6159581.

38: Sluydts V, Sarathchandra SR, Piscitelli AP, Van Houtte N, Gryseels S, Mayer-Scholl A, Bier NS, Htwe NM, Jacob J. Ecology and distribution of *Leptospira* spp., reservoir hosts and environmental interaction in Sri Lanka, with identification of a new strain. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* 2022 Sep 16;16(9):e0010757. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0010757. PMID: 36112668; PMCID: PMC9518908.

39: Schiettekatte O, Bourhy P. Isolation, Purification, and Characterization of Leptophages. *Methods Mol Biol.* 2020;2134:67-75. doi: 10.1007/978-1-0716-0459-5_7. PMID: 32632860.

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43: Hacker KP, Sacramento GA, Cruz JS, de Oliveira D, Nery N Jr, Lindow JC, Carvalho M, Hagan J, Diggle PJ, Begon M, Reis MG, Wunder EA Jr, Ko AI, Costa F. Influence of Rainfall on *Leptospira* Infection and Disease in a Tropical Urban Setting, Brazil. *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2020 Feb;26(2):311-314. doi: 10.3201/eid2602.190102. PMID: 31961288; PMCID: PMC6986844.

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46: Lau CL, Watson CH, Lowry JH, David MC, Craig SB, Wynwood SJ, Kama M, Nilles EJ. Human Leptospirosis Infection in Fiji: An Eco-epidemiological Approach to Identifying Risk Factors and Environmental Drivers for Transmission. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2016 Jan 28;10(1):e0004405. doi: 10.1371/journal.pntd.0004405. PMID: 26820752; PMCID: PMC4731082.

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57: Ji J, Wang W, Xiang S, Wei X, Pang G, Shi H, Dong J, Pang J. Diagnosis of leptospira by metagenomics next-generation sequencing with extracorporeal membrane oxygenation support: a case report. *BMC Infect Dis*. 2023 Nov 13;23(1):788. doi: 10.1186/s12879-023-08793-w. PMID: 37957556; PMCID: PMC10644436.

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